

and Cu(II) ions were found to interfere. The interference of Fe(III) was removed by adding tartarate.

Separation and determination of Cu(II), Ni(II) and V(V): A mixture consisting of Cu(II), Ni(II) and V(V) was diluted to 150 ml and its pH was adjusted with HClO₄ and NH₄OH between 2.2-2.4. The solution was heated between 40-50° and 1% ethanolic reagent solution was added. A blue ppt of Cu(II) complex appeared and it was digested on a water-bath between 70-80° for ½ hr. It was then filtered through a weighed sintered-glass crucible and washed with warm water. Finally it was washed with 10% ethanol and dried between 100-110° to a constant weight. The ppt was found to possess the composition [Cu(C₁₁H₈N₂SO₃)(H₂O)₃]. The washings and filtrate were collected and Ni(II) was precipitated between the pH 2.5-3.1 as in the case of Cu(II) complex. The Ni(II) complex possessed the composition [Ni(C₁₁H₈N₂SO₃)(H₂O)₃]. Finally in the filtrate of washings of Ni(II) estimation, V(V) was determined as described earlier.

Estimation of V(V) in ferro-vanadium alloy: A ferro-vanadium alloy containing 35-80% of vanadium was used. A known weight of the alloy was dissolved in conc. H₂SO₄. The solution contained ions like As, Sb, Mo, Fe, W, CrO₄²⁻ and PO₄³⁻ which interfere (W and PO₄³⁻ ion do not interfere) in the quantitative estimation of V(V).

Vanadium was separated and estimated from these ions as follows. The sulphuric acid solution of the alloy was neutralised, rendered faintly acidic and an excess of sulphurous acid added. CO₂ was passed to remove excess of SO₂. H₂S was then passed to precipitate out As₂S₃ and Sb₂S₃. Molybdenum was also removed by passing H₂S under pressure. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness, the residue extracted with water and SO₂ gas was passed until chromium was reduced to trivalent, iron to bivalent while vanadium to tetravalent states. Cr(III) was precipitated out by 10% NaOH solution and removed. The filtrate was treated with 30% H₂O₂ which oxidised Fe(II) to Fe(III) and V(IV) to V(V). Addition of 10% NaOH to this solution precipitated Fe(OH)₃ which was washed with 1% Na₂CO₃ and the washing added to the original filtrate containing vanadium. The process of precipitation of iron was repeated till it was free from vanadium. All the filtrates and washings were collected in which V(V) was estimated by H₂PB in pH 3.2-4.0 as described and weighed as VO₂(C₁₁H₈N₂SO₃)(H₂O).

Elemental analysis and molecular weight of the V(V) complex (337) determined ebulliometrically by Gallenkamp semi micro ebulliometer in dioxane gave its composition as [VO₂(C₁₁H₈N₂SO₃)(H₂O)] having 1:1 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry. It was found diamagnetic. The molecular weight suggests its monomeric nature.

In the ir spectra of H₂PB three bands were observed at 3200 cm⁻¹, 1610 cm⁻¹ and 1180 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{NH}, ν_{C-N} and ν_{as}(SO₃H) respectively.

The absence of ν_{NH} in the V(V) complex indicates the involvement of imino nitrogen in chelate formation. The band at 1180 cm⁻¹ also disappeared suggesting coordination through the sulphonate group. ν_{C-N} of H₂PB around 1610 cm⁻¹ was shifted to lower frequency side (1580 cm⁻¹) on chelation indicating the participation of azomethine nitrogen in coordination. The appearance of two new bands in the region 595 cm⁻¹ and 510 cm⁻¹ in the V(V) complex may reflect the M-O and M-N bands. The V(V) complex also exhibits a broad band around 3430-3400 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{OH} of water.

The deprotonated ligand forms a stable chelate with V(V) involving two chelate rings of which one is five-membered and the other six-membered. Thus due to its higher stability the complex becomes totally insoluble.

The structures of the ligand and its V(V) complex are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Vanadium (V) complex of *o*-(*N*- α -Pyrrolideneimino) Benzene Sulphonic Acid.

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References

1. H. H. WILLARD, E. L. MARTIN and R. FELTHAM, *Anal. Chem.*, 1953, **25**, 1863.
2. R. BERG, *Enke*, Stuttgart, 1953, **65**, 64.
3. C. P. GUPTA, N. K. SANKHLA and R. K. MEHTA, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1979, **321**, 691.
4. C. P. GUPTA, N. K. SANKHLA and R. K. MEHTA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 1892.
5. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical Uses of EDTA", D. Van Nostrand Company, New York, 1957, p. 205.

Iodometric Determination of Milligram Amounts of Semicarbazide Hydrochloride by Hypiodite Oxidation

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A simple, rapid and accurate method for the determination of semicarbazide hydrochloride based on its oxidation with sodium hypiodite is described. The procedure can be applied for evaluating 1-20 mg of semicarbazide with an accuracy

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of 0.1-0.3%. The effect of different factors governing the stoichiometry of the reaction has also been investigated.

Gasometric estimation^{1,2} of semicarbazide involves its decomposition and measurement of the liberated nitrogen or ammonia. Oxidimetric determinations are based on its oxidation with diethylene tetra-ammonium cerate³, potassium ferricyanide⁴, potassium bromate⁵, potassium persulphate⁶, sodium metavanadate⁷, potassium periodate⁸, thallium(III)⁹ and mercury(II)-EDTA complex. Most of these require the addition of a buffer or a catalyst.

The present communication describes a rapid and convenient method for the determination of semicarbazide hydrochloride based on its oxidation with sodium hypoiodite. The procedure does not require the addition of a buffer or a catalyst, being iodometric gives sharp end-point and can be applied for determining as low as 1 mg of semicarbazide with an accuracy of about 0.3%.

Semicarbazide reacts with iodine in accordance with the equation :

According to Bartlet¹¹ the reaction is slow but can be fast if the test sample is neutralised and sufficient phosphate buffer is added. The reaction of semicarbazide hydrochloride with iodine has been investigated under a variety of experimental conditions from analytical view point. Based on a critical evaluation of the results of these experiments an iodometric procedure has been evolved for determination of semicarbazide hydrochloride at milligram level.

Experimental

Reagents : The following solutions were prepared using analytical grade chemicals. Sodium thiosulphate, 0.1 *M* was prepared by standardisation against potassium iodate. 0.05, 0.01 and 0.005 *M* solutions were prepared by diluting 0.1 *M* solution with conductivity water. Iodine, 0.1 *M* (containing 25 g potassium iodide per litre) was standardised by titration with thiosulphate; 0.05, 0.025 and 0.005 *M* solutions were then prepared by diluting the 0.1 *M* solution. Sodium hydroxide, 1 *M* solution, Sulphuric acid 2 *M* solution, Starch, 1% aqueous solution.

Semicarbazide hydrochloride solution was standardised by titration with potassium iodate in presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid by Andrew's method¹². 0.1, 0.025, 0.01, 0.005, 0.0025 and 0.00125 *M* solutions were prepared by suitably diluting the standardised solution using conductivity water.

Procedure : 5 to 20 ml of semicarbazide hydrochloride solution containing 0.012-0.2 m mole of the substance is pipetted into an iodine flask. Distilled water is added to make the total volume

50-60 ml. A measured excess (100-200%) of iodine and 5 ml of 1 *M* sodium hydroxide is introduced and the flask is stoppered. The contents are mixed by swirling and allowed to react for 2-3 mins. 2 ml of 2 *M* sulphuric acid is added and the iodine is titrated with standard thiosulphate solution. An appropriate blank determination is run. 1 ml of 0.01 *M* sodium thiosulphate \equiv 0.1876 mg semicarbazide.

Results and Discussion

The proposed iodometric method was applied for the determination of semicarbazide hydrochloride at six concentration levels containing 0.01-0.2 m mole of the substance. The results presented in Table 1 are calculated from six determinations. The recovery studies show that the procedure is accurate to within 0.3%.

TABLE 1—MICRODETERMINATION OF SEMICARBAZIDE HYDROCHLORIDE

mg taken	Proposed Method		Bartlet's Method		Andrew's Method	
	*Recovery %	Standard deviation %	*Recovery %	Standard deviation %	*Recovery %	Standard deviation %
27.875	100.07	0.15	100.52	0.20	100.6	0.22
11.153	99.84	0.11	99.39	0.36	100.5	0.26
5.576	99.85	0.18	103.82	0.32	101.9	0.20
2.783	99.75	0.12	102.3	0.42	102.8	0.42
1.394	99.70	0.22	103.2	0.38	104.1	0.38

* Calculated from six determinations.

The gasometric estimation of semicarbazide by its decomposition and subsequent measurement of the liberated nitrogen or ammonia is cumbersome. Most oxidimetric methods use either a buffer or a catalyst to promote the reaction. In certain procedures the detection of end-point is not convenient and easy and hence accurate results cannot be obtained when the sample solution is dilute. The procedures recommended by Bartlet¹¹ and Kurtenacker and Kubina¹² give good results up to 0.01 *M* but with more dilute solution significant error is observed as is shown by the comparative study recorded in Table 1. The proposed method is simple, rapid and accurate. The experimental conditions are not critical. The sample solution need not be neutralised to pH 7 nor the addition of a buffer or a catalyst is required. The procedure being iodometric gives sharp end-point and can be readily applied for quantitative analysis of sample solutions containing milligram amounts of semicarbazide hydrochloride. It should, however, be noted that if the concentration of the test solution is more than 0.01 *M*, the total volume of the reaction mixture must be made to 50-60 ml by adding distilled water otherwise positive error creeps in. With dilute (concentration less than 0.01 *M*) test solutions the dilution of reaction mixture is not necessary.

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References

1. H. MC KENNIS and A. S. YARD, U. S. Dept. Com., Office Tech. Serv. P₂ Rept., 1957, **143**, 13.
2. G. BOURJOL, *Chim. Anal.*, 1959, **41**, 231.
3. B. SINGH, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1957, **17**, 467.
4. I. KASA and L. ERDEY, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1963, **39**, 21.
5. J. VULTERIN, *Talanta*, 1963, **10**, 891; *Collection Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1963, **28**, 1393.
6. B. SINGH, S. S. SAHOTA and I. SINGH, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1958, **162**, 256.
7. B. SINGH and S. S. SAHOTA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1957, **17**, 258.
8. A. BERKA and J. ZYKA, *Chim. Listy*, 1956, **50**, 314.
9. A. BERKA, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1963, **193**, 276.
10. B. BUDESINSKY, *Collection Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1961, **26**, 781.
11. P. D. BARTLETT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 2853.
12. A. KURTNACKER and H. KUBINA, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1924, **64**, 388.

Protein and Amino Acid Composition of Certain Plants of Cucurbitaceae

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A number of plants of the family cucurbitaceae grow in various parts of the country and possess several medicinal properties. The seeds of *Citrullus colocynthis* are used as nerve tonic¹. These plants grow abundantly in the Rajasthan desert. The seeds are rich in protein and possess all the essential amino acids except tryptophan². In the present investigation four plants of the family were examined.

The seeds were collected locally and identified systematically. The seedcoats were removed and the kernels defatted with petroleum ether b.p. (60-80°). The protein percentage was determined

* For correspondence.

by Modified Kjeldahl's method and also with spectrophotometric method³ which are in good agreement.

The defatted seed meal was extracted several times with 10% sodium chloride solution and the protein was precipitated with trichloroacetic acid. The precipitated protein was hydrolysed with 5.5 N HCl in sealed glass tubes. The acid free hydrolysate after repeated distillation *in vacuo* was subjected to paper chromatographic analysis. The amino acids were separated by two dimensional chromatography on Whatman No. 1 paper by butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5) and phenol : water (3 : 1) and were identified with spray reagents⁴⁻⁶.

Results and Discussion

The nitrogen and protein content of the seeds is given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Name of the plant	Weight of sample in g.	%N ₂	%protein
<i>Citrullus vulgaris</i>	0.1056	6.5	40.57
<i>Cucumis Melo</i>	0.0988	7.99	49.93
<i>Cucumis melo utilissimus</i>	0.1002	8.3	57.87
<i>Lagenaria vulgaris</i>	0.1002	7.15	44.68

Table 1 shows the nitrogen percentage as well as the protein percentage in the samples. It is interesting to note that all the plants analysed show high protein content. They also contain all the essential amino acids except Tryptophan. Looking at the high protein content these seeds can be suggested as cheap source of protein.

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References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", 1956; C. S. I. R. Publication, New Delhi.
2. S. S. JOSHI, R. K. SRIVASTAVA and S. S. NIGAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 747.
3. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis" Third Edition, 1975, p. 784.
4. E. STAHL, "Thin layer chromatography" Second Ed., 1969, 749.
5. A. SAIFER and I. ORESKES, *Science*, 1954, **119**, 124.
6. J. B. JEPSON and I. SMITH, *Nature*, 1953, **172**, 1100.